

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE INDICATORS FOR THREE VARIETIES OF THE SPECIES *CYPRINUS CARPIO*

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Abstract

This research examines the influence of internal factors on the growth patterns of three *Cyprinus carpio* varieties, all originating from Romania. The study aims to clarify the growth patterns characteristic of each variety and their implications for aquaculture and ecological management. The fish were evaluated in terms of total length, maximum height, and weight at four developmental stages. Weight, specific growth rate, relative growth rate, profile index, and condition factor were calculated and studied.

The results revealed important differences between the varieties in terms of growth efficiency, body shape development, and general physiological condition throughout life. The Romanian varieties showed better growth in the late stages, the condition factor according to Fulton, and the profile index showed significant variations between varieties and growth stages, suggesting a different energy distribution and morphological adjustments. These results highlight the complex interactions between genetic traits and developmental processes in carp species, providing useful information for breeding programs, aquaculture methods, and ecological management strategies, but also the importance of strategies adapted to each variety in carp cultivation and conservation efforts.

Introduction

Identifying the internal factors that influence fish growth is vital for optimizing aquaculture methods, managing wild fish populations, and anticipating ecosystem responses to environmental changes, as fish development dynamics have long been a topic of interest in fish science, aquaculture, and fisheries management [1,6]. The importance of studying them is also emphasized by the current context of climate change, where species adaptability is an essential criterion in the conservation of aquatic biodiversity.

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This research aims to clarify the complex interactions of internal factors that regulate fish growth. Fish development is a multifactorial phenomenon influenced by both external conditions and internal physiological processes. Although external factors, such as temperature, food quantity and water quality, have been intensively studied, the internal processes that regulate development and variations between individuals and species are still poorly understood, but understanding these processes could provide a solid scientific basis for improving the productivity and sustainability of aquaculture [2].

Hereditary factors have a significant impact on the variability in fish growth. The burgeoning field of epigenetics has complicated our understanding of growth regulation, suggesting that environmental factors influence the pattern of gene expression across generations [3].

Metabolic processes, such as protein degradation, fat metabolism, and energy distribution, are essential for fish development [4]. However, the molecular mechanisms that determine metabolic efficiency and their link to growth performance are not fully elucidated. Also, the influence of intestinal flora on fish metabolism and development has begun to attract attention, opening new directions for research [5, 8].

This study aims to integrate existing knowledge and provide new insights into the complex network of internal factors affecting fish growth. Our results could have important implications for selective breeding programs, feed formulation strategies and the development of new growth-enhancing techniques. The research contributes to a deeper understanding of the endogenous mechanisms that support fish growth, with the potential to improve aquatic practices and provide more accurate models for fisheries resource management.

Material and Methods:

This research analyzed three varieties of common carp *Cyprinus carpio* Linnæus, 1758: Koi, Ineu, and Podul Iloaiei. The three types were cultured within the Research and Development Station for Aquaculture and Aquatic Ecology, and the fish were kept in earthen ponds (average depth of 1.6 m and 0.5 ha) exposed to environmental light and temperature conditions. Water parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH and ammonia concentrations were checked daily, maintaining an optimal temperature in earthen ponds is an essential element for obtaining healthy and uniform growth, although in such systems the temperature cannot be controlled mechanically, it can be regulated effectively through natural and technical measures such as: correct choice of location, optimal pond depth, management of water intake and vegetation control.

Sampling was carried out in four developmental stages, 6 days after hatching the initial measurements were taken marking the completion of yolk sac absorption and the transition to exogenous feeding, 0⁺ approximately 3 months representing the completion of the first growth period, 1⁺ around 16 months and comprising post-winter recovery and second summer growth and 2⁺ around two summers and winters representing fish of the appropriate size and at each stage 20 individuals from each variety were randomly selected to be measured. The following morphological parameters were evaluated for each specimen: total length was measured from the tip of the snout to the tip of the caudal fin, with an ichthyometer, maximum height was determined in the deepest area of the body, using an ichthyometer, mass was calculated using

an electronic balance. All measurements were performed by specialized personnel to maintain uniformity and reduce the stress of handling the biological material.

The analyzed parameters targeted the evolution of body mass, expressed by weight GAIN (WG), specific growth rate (SGR), and relative growth rate reported to the initial weight of the specimens (RGR), Profile Index, and Fulton Condition Factor. The condition factor represents an essential biometric index, used in the evaluation of physiological condition and growth performance. It expresses the relationship between body mass and total length, being an integrative indicator of the health status, the degree of nutrition, and the adaptability of fish varieties.

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). First, the data sets were checked for normality of distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test, and homogeneity of variances was assessed using the Levene test. One-way ANOVA was applied to compare growth indices between the three carp varieties at each life stage. In cases where statistically significant differences were found ($p < 0.05$), the Tukey HSD post-hoc test was used to identify groups between which there were significant differences.

Results and Discussion:

The analysis of weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR), and relative growth rate (RGR) of the three varieties of *Cyprinus carpio* highlights the genetic diversity of the studied populations. The varieties Podul Iloaiei and Ineu demonstrated superior performance in stages 1⁺ and 2⁺, suggesting an increased potential for productivity. These results are consistent with previous research that reported significant variations in growth rates. The Koi variety presented a distinct pattern, with lower initial weight, but higher SGR and RGR in stage 2⁺, reflecting its ornamental [7].

The parameters analyzed included weight variation (WG), specific growth rate (SGR) and growth rate relative to initial weight (RGR). Weight variation, in stage 0⁺, the Podul Iloaiei variety presented a significantly higher weight variation of 35,50g, compared to the Koi 34,43g, and Ineu 34,24g, varieties (Table 1).

Table 1. Weight increase of *Cyprinus carpio* varieties in various ontogenetic stages

<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	WG0 ⁺	WG1 ⁺	WG2 ⁺
Podul Iloaiei	35,50	585,78	856,34
Ineu	34,24	557,76	850,23
Koi	34,43	75,46	398,98

Values are presented as mean, there are significant differences between varieties (Tukey HSD Test, $p < 0.05$). WG-Weight gain, calculated as Final weight- Initial weight, WG0⁺- Weight gain at one year and summer stage, WG1⁺- Weight gain at one year and summer stage, WG2⁺- Weight gain at two years and summer stage. Within stage 1⁺, Podul Iloaiei recorded the highest WG1⁺- (585,78G), followed by Ineu (557,76g) and Koi (75,46g). All these differences were statistically significant (Table 1). In stage 2⁺, the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties had comparable WG2⁺ values (856,34 and 850,23g) without significant differences. However, the Koi variety had a much lower WG (398,98g) compared to the other varieties (Table 1).

Specific Growth Rate (SGR), In phase 0⁺, the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties presented higher SGR values (2,89 and 2,61g, respectively), compared to the Koi variety (2,10g), (Table 2). Stage 1⁺, the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties showed the highest SGR for both, followed by the Koi variety (0,15g).

All variations were statistically significant (Tukey HSD test, p<0.05). (Table 2). In stage 2⁺, the Koi variety recorded the highest SGR (0.20G), while the Ineu and Podul Iloaiei varieties had the lowest values (0.5 for each) (Table 2).

Table 2. Specific growth rate of *Cyprinus carpio* species at different growth stages

<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	RGR0⁺	RGR1⁺	RGR2⁺
Podul Iloaiei	320,34	4,66	0,40
Ineu	356,34	4,55	0,38
Koi	510,60	0,67	0,96

Values are presented as mean, there are significant differences between varieties (Tukey HSD TEST, p<0.05). SGR-Specific growth rate, calculated as In Final Weight- In Initial Weight, SGR0⁺-Specific growth rate in the one-year-old fry stage, SGR1⁺-Specific growth rate at one year and in the one-year-old stage, SGR2⁺-Specific growth rate at two years and in the one-year-old stage.

<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	SGR0⁺	SGR1⁺	SGR2⁺
Podul Iloaiei	2,89	0,30	0,5
Ineu	2,61	0,30	0,5
Koi	2,10	0,15	0,20

At the 0⁺ level, the Koi variety demonstrated the most remarkable RGR (510.60). The Ineu and Podul Iloaiei varieties showed intermediate values without significant discrepancies compared to the other varieties (Table 3).

Table 3. Relative growth rate of *Cyprinus carpio* species in different growth stages

Values are presented as mean, there are significant differences between varieties (Tukey HSD Test, p<0.05). RGR-Relative growth rate, calculated as (Final weight-Initial weight)/ Initial weight x 100. RGR0⁺-Relative growth rate at one-year-old fry stage, RGR1⁺-Relative growth rate at one year and at one summer stage, RGR2⁺-Relative growth rate at two years and at one summer stage.

In stage 1⁺, the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties demonstrated the highest relative growth rate (RGR). All differences were found to be statistically significant (Table 3).

In stage 2⁺, the Koi variety recorded the highest growth (RGR), which was significantly different from all other types. The varieties Ineu and Podul Iloaiei had lower (RGR) values, without significant differences between them.

The index profile, defined as the ratio between maximum height and total length, was studied for three varieties of *Cyprinus carpio* (Podul Iloaiei, Koi and Ineu) at four distinct moments of development. (Table 4).

Table 4. Profile index of the varieties of the species *Cyprinus carpio*

<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	7 days	0 ⁺	1 ⁺	2 ⁺
Podul Iloaiei	4,34	2,55	2,23	2,19
Ineu	3,0	2,54	2,22	2,17
Koi	3,80	2,96	2,50	2,18

Values are presented as mean, there are significant differences between varieties (Tukey HSD Test, $p < 0.05$). The profile index was calculated as Maximum Height/Total Length. Measurements were performed 7 days after hatching, at the summer fry stage 0⁺, at one year, and summer stage 1⁺, and at two years and one summer stage 2⁺.

At seven days after hatching, notable variations were observed between the different varieties. In this sense, the Podul Iloaiei variety had the highest profile index (4.34), followed by the Koi (3.80) and Ineu (3.0) varieties (Table 4).

At the 0⁺ stage, the Koi variety recorded the highest profile index value (2.96), which was significantly different from the other varieties. Podul Iloaiei and Ineu had lower, similar values (2.55 and 2.54), with no significant difference between them. (Table 4).

In stage 1⁺, the Koi variety maintained the highest profile index (2.55). The Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties also had lower, similar values (2.23 and 2.22). All differences were statistically significant, except for those between the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties. (Table 4).

For stage 2⁺, the varieties Podul Iloaiei, Koi, and Ineu showed lower values, with no significant differences between them. (Table 4).

The profile index generally decreased as the fish reached maturity, with the highest values being recorded at seven days post-hatch, while the lowest were observed at stage 2⁺, for most varieties. However, the rate and degree of decrease varied between varieties, Ineu showing a steep decrease from 3.0 at 7 days to 2.54 at stage 0⁺, after which it stabilized around 2.22 and 2.17 in the following growth stages.

The variety Podul Iloaiei showed the most significant change, decreasing from 4.34 at 7 days to 2.55 at 0⁺, later stabilizing around 2.18 for the following growth stages. The Koi variety showed a distinct pattern, dropping from 3.80 at 7 days to 2.96 at 0⁺, but subsequently maintained a higher profile index compared to other species at 1⁺, before aligning with the other at 2⁺.

Fulton's condition factor was studied for three varieties of the species *Cyprinus carpio* at four different growth stages. At 7 days after hatching, notable differences were observed between the varieties, Ineu having the highest Fulton index (150.23), followed by the varieties Podul Iloaiei (64.98) and Koi (39.23).

At stage 0⁺, the variety Koi presented the highest value (1.89), while the varieties Podul Iloaiei and Ineu had similar and lower values (1.65 and 1.62). For stage 1⁺, the variety Podul Iloaiei showed the highest Fulton index (3.98), closely followed by the variety Ineu (3.89). The variety Koi had a considerably lower value (0.73) compared to the other species. Regarding stage 2⁺, the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties obtained the highest Fulton indices (4.07 and 4.04), with no significant difference between them, while the Koi variety recorded the lowest Fulton index (1.69).

These findings highlight significant differences in body shape development between different varieties of the *Cyprinus carpio* species during their ability to adapt to varied environments and suitability in various aquaculture systems [8,17,18].

These observations on Fulton's condition factor, together with the performance and growth profile of the index, provide a detailed view of the developmental pattern of these varieties of the species *Cyprinus carpio*.

The observed changes highlight the need to consider species-specific characteristics in aquaculture management and ecological studies [9,16].

Future studies should examine both the genetic and environmental factors contributing to these variations in condition factor, as well as their implications for the health efficiency and adaptation of fish in diverse aquatic environments.

The diversity in growth and morphological development observed among the different varieties of *Cyprinus carpio* analyzed has a significant impact on aquaculture practices. The superior performance of the Podul Iloaiei and Ineu varieties at more advanced stages suggests that they have the potential to increase production efficiency in commercial aquaculture environments.

However, the distinct growth pattern of the Koi variety illustrates the need to consider the entire developmental trajectory when selecting species for cultivation, given that late-developing species can reach the desired final sizes [10,13,14,15,19].

Variations in the profile index could affect the adaptability of varieties within different aquaculture systems and natural environments. Species with lower profile indices in adult stages, such as the Ineu and Podul Iloaiei varieties, might be better suited to high-density aquaculture systems or habitats with stronger water currents due to potential better swimming efficiency [11,12].

Conclusions:

This extensive study on two Romanian varieties of *Cyprinus carpio* (Ineu and Podul Iloaiei) and the ornamental Koi variety highlighted significant differences between them in terms of growth performance, body shape development, and physiological status during several growth stages. The observed variations in body weight, specific growth rate, and relative growth between the Romanian species highlight opportunities for improving selection programs to increase aquaculture productivity in the area.

The distinct patterns of profile indices between these species suggest specific adaptations to the diverse aquatic environments encountered in Romania, with the potential to influence both the design of local aquaculture systems and ecological management strategies.

These results may inform future research on the genetic and environmental factors responsible for phenotypic variation among Romanian carp varieties. Such studies could lead to improvements in breeding programs, more efficient aquatic practices adapted to local conditions, and a deeper understanding of the ecological implications associated with the diversity of the *Cyprinus carpio* species in Romanian ecosystems.

Including the ornamental Koi variety provides important comparative insights, highlighting the plasticity of the species under various selection pressures. This information

will support the sustainable development of carp aquaculture in Romania and the competent management of wild populations in various local ecosystems.

It also highlights the importance of conserving and studying local species as valuable genetic resources for future aquaculture development and biodiversity conservation efforts.

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